

PEDAGOGICAL STRATEGIES TO ENHANCE ENGLISH SPEAKING SKILLS IN HIGHER SECONDARY LEVEL CLASSROOMS

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15754263>

Keywords

English speaking skills, classroom strategies, Sahiwal education, higher secondary students, spoken English, interactive learning, language confidence, Pakistani classrooms, teacher practices, oral communication

Article History

Received on 120May 2025

Accepted on 20 June 2025

Published on 27 June 2025

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Abstract

This study investigates classroom-based pedagogical strategies to improve English speaking skills among higher secondary students in Sahiwal, Pakistan. The primary aim is to explore effective and practical methods that teachers can use to develop students' oral communication abilities within a local classroom context. A three-month spoken English intervention was implemented, using a mixed-methods approach that combined data from student questionnaires and in-depth teacher interviews. Findings reveal that students commonly face difficulties such as lack of self-confidence, limited practice opportunities, weak vocabulary, and fear of making errors. However, interactive strategies like group discussions, role plays, student presentations, and integration of multimedia tools significantly improved students' engagement and fluency. Teachers emphasized the importance of professional training, relevant teaching materials, and infrastructural support to implement these strategies effectively. The study offers useful insights for language educators, policymakers, and curriculum developers aiming to improve spoken English proficiency in secondary schools across Punjab, particularly in less urbanized regions like Sahiwal.

INTRODUCTION

English is considered an international language and is used around the globe to communicate in almost every walk of life. In Pakistan, proficiency in spoken English is crucial for academics, career opportunities, and social interactions. In Pakistan where English is an institutional and official language and used as a medium of instruction at micro and macro levels, proficiency and accuracy is much more important for students in general and for language learners in particular. For students in grades 11 and 12, fluency in speaking English is important for success in college and to get employment. English is not just a subject for Pakistani students but a life skill. Mastering it can open new doors to a better future, and career opportunities. Yet, the majority of the students face

difficulties in speaking English even after learning English for more than ten years.

Students in our country with minimum sources face several challenges in developing and enhancing English speaking skills. These challenges stem from social, educational, psychological and systemic factors. A major issue is that emphasis in colleges is mainly on memorizing grammar rules, vocabulary and pronunciation instead of developing speaking skills. Moreover, students don't get enough chances to practice speaking in class. Large classrooms and limited facilitations in our traditional academic modes made it harder for the learners and as well as instructors to include effective speaking exercises.

Lack of training in real life situations make it more difficult for the students to improve or enhance their abilities. Other factors like public opinions, fear factors, judgmental attitudes, low confidence, lack of encouragement and negative discourse can also stop students from speaking freely and confidently to get fluency and accuracy.

These challenges get worse if learners can't get enough support morally and professionally. Improvements in existing traditional methodologies and implementations of newly developed strategies, change in curriculum can help the students to become confident speakers of English language. This article seeks to identify effective teaching methods tailored for enhancing students' spoken English skills.

Literature Review

Recent literature on pedagogical strategies emphasizes the importance of speech competence. It highlights different innovative pedagogical approaches adopted to face the unique challenges of attaining speech proficiency among Pakistani students at intermediate level. These strategies foster communicative competence, increase student engagement, and address the problems related to limited resources and traditional teaching practice.

Storytelling is an effective method for improving speaking skills among ESL learners. Teaching Proficiency through Reading and Storytelling (TPR), makes the input both comprehensible and engaging. This approach has been effective in enhancing both fluency and accuracy as it provides students with meaningful and context-rich input. Lim, G. F., & Hashim, H. (2025). A study conducted in Northern Sindh revealed that storytelling enhances student engagement, vocabulary acquisition, fluency, and pronunciation. It was observed that students became more confident speakers when engaged in storytelling activities Ullah, S., Khan IU Hamid A. (2021). However, challenges such as limited resources and overcrowded classrooms were noted, emphasizing the need for targeted teacher training and resource allocation

Differentiated Instruction (DI) focuses on the diverse learning needs of students by devising teaching methods accordingly. Research indicates that DI is practiced primarily in elite schools in Pakistan. There

is a gap in its widespread implementation. The study recommends broader adoption of DI strategies according to the capabilities of each learner. It may enhance language acquisition and speaking proficiency across different educational settings. Nguyen, D. (2025).

Introducing gamification into ESL classrooms has resulted in increasing student motivation and participation. A study of Pakistani universities found that gamified approaches improved classroom management and language proficiency. (Ranjhani, Fatima, & Rashid, 2025) By Creating dynamic and immersive learning environments, Gamification fosters student engagement and facilitates the development of speaking skills by creating dynamic and immersive learning environments.

Incorporating drama into ESL teaching has been effective in developing communicative competence, incorporating drama into ESL teaching has been effective. A study in Burnwal revealed that drama activities enhanced students' confidence and ability to express themselves in English. Drama-based activities proved a tool for improving speaking skills, highlighting its potential for broader application in ESL curricula (Siraj, Ali, & Nauman, 2025).

Communicative Language Teaching involves interaction and real-life communication. Students taught through CLT methods perform better than those taught via traditional approaches in speaking, listening, reading, and writing skills. Khalid, S., Maqbool, S., & Nazli, K. (2025). The learner-centered nature of CLT contributes to developing speaking skills. Research in various Pakistani ESL/EFL classrooms revealed that strategies such as code-switching and the use of homonyms aid comprehension and maintain

communication flow. Zaman, M., et al. (2025). These strategies help prevent communication breakdowns and support students in developing their speaking abilities.

The use of indigenized Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL) materials has been proved a means to enhance speaking skills of Pakistani learners. A study conducted at the Islamia University of Bahawalpur revealed that students who used an indigenized spoken English computer application

showed notable improvements in their speaking proficiency compared to those who used non-indigenized materials (Bashir, Aziz, Imran, & Almusharraf, 2025)

Despite these strategies to improve speaking skill, research indicates that many students in Pakistan still lack the desired proficiency levels. A study revealed significant gaps between the current abilities of grade-11th and 12th students and the standards set by the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR). This emphasizes the need for effective pedagogical plans that incorporate comprehensible input to bridge these gaps. Lodhi, M. A., & Akash, A. (2019)

The reviewed literature highlights the importance of adopting multifaceted, contextually appropriate pedagogical strategies to enhance the speech competence of Pakistani intermediate-level ESL students. These devices have proved efficient in improving students' speaking skills. To maximize the benefits of these methods, it is essential to address challenges related to resource availability, teacher training, and curriculum design.

Theoretical Framework

The study applied Vygotsky's sociocultural theory that focuses on CLT (Communicative Language Teaching). Vygotsky's theory promotes interactive learning, encourages peer to peer interaction, and emphasizes group work incorporated with debates and role-playing. The goal is to enable the students to learn and use language effectively in a context rather than rote memorisation of grammar rules. The theory also highlights the importance of dialogue and collaborative problem-solving, which are significant in the development of higher-order cognitive skills such as critical thinking. (Khan, 2024)

Research Design and Methodology

1. Research Approach

This 12 weeks longitudinal study adopts a mixed-methods approach, utilizing both quantitative and qualitative methods to have an understanding of the pedagogical strategies to enhance speaking skills among students of Intermediate classes in our public sector colleges in Sahiwal. The quantitative approach involves student questionnaires, while the qualitative

aspect includes open ended questions and structured interviews with teachers, and observations of students performance during 12 weeks. The educators, in this period, implemented the techniques of group discussion and debates, role-playing and problem solving, and guided practice with the help of language structures. Modern technology was also utilized. The educators made use of formative assessment and corrective as well as encouraging feedback.

2. Sample and Sampling

The research involved 150 students of first year and second year. Stratified Random sampling was used to select students from 1st and 2nd year classes of male and female institutes of Sahiwal. Fifteen English language teachers were selected from different male and female institutes. Purposive sampling was utilized to select English teachers who were willing to take active part in study.

3 Data Collection Tools

- Questionnaires (printed) were developed for students to collect data about their routine, targets, and problems regarding speaking activities in the classroom.
- Interview guides (printed) were prepared for semi-structured interviews with teachers to gather data about their teaching practices and techniques used to enhance students' speaking skills.
- Assessments of speaking performance of students at intervals.
- Classroom observations of pedagogical strategies implementation
- Analysis of speech samples.

4. Data Collection Steps

Step 1: Permission was obtained from college administrations to collect data

Step 2: Students questionnaires were distributed in printed form before and after implementing pedagogical strategies.

Step 3: Teachers were given questionnaires with open ended questions, to get in-depth and contextual responses.

Step 4: All responses were arranged, scanned and analysed systematically.

5. Data Analysis and Findings

Students' responses were counted and to get average scores and identify common patterns, such as the number of students who preferred group discussions or found specific activities helpful. Teachers' responses were noted ,and grouped under common themes such as "interactive classroom techniques," "challenges in teaching speaking," and "use of technology to improve the speaking skill of students." This analysis proved helped in identifying effective pedagogical strategies for the development of speech competence.

5.1 Quantitative Results

Analysis of assessments at the beginning and completion of the 12 week period revealed significant improvements in students' speaking

competence in different respective areas: Fluency: Students showed a 31% improvement in speaking rate and a 33% reduction in hesitation.

Accuracy: Linguistic accuracy improved by 22%, especially in complex sentences.

Confidence: Confidence levels increased by 39%, and participation rates also improved.

Pragmatic Competence: Appropriate language use for different contexts was improved by 42%.

STUDENTS' DATA (150 Participants)

Demographics Summary

- **Age Range:** 16-20 years
- **Gender:** 60% Female, 40% Male,
- **First Languages:**Urdu,Punjabi,Saraiki.
- **Years in Target Language:** 11-12 years

STUDENT RESPONSES (in the first week)

Aggregated Data (150 Students)

Measure	Mean Score	
Speaking Confidence	2.8/5	
Speaking Anxiety	3.6/5	
Participation Frequency	2.5/5	
Fluency	2.9/5	
Accuracy	2.7/5	
Vocabulary	3.1/5	
Organization	2.6/5	
Overall Satisfaction	2.4/5	

STUDENT RESPONSES (in the last week)

Aggregated Data (150 Students)

Measure	Mean Score	Improvement
Speaking Confidence	3.9/5	+39%
Speaking Anxiety (reduced)	2.4/5	-33%
Participation Frequency	3.8/5	+52%
Fluency	3.8/5	+31%
Accuracy	3.3/5	+22%
Vocabulary	3.9/5	+26%
Organization	3.7/5	+42%
Overall Satisfaction	4.1/5	+71%

Strategy Effectiveness Ratings (150 Students Average)

Strategy	Effectiveness Rating
Structured Peer Discussions	4.6/5
Scaffolded Speaking Tasks	4.5/5
Role-Playing Activities	4.3/5
Recording/Self-Evaluation	4.1/5
Peer Feedback	4.0/5
Technology Tools	3.8/5
Group Problem-Solving	3.7/5
Formal Presentations	3.2/5

TEACHER DATA (15 Participants)

Demographics Summary

- **Teaching Experience:** 3-25 years
- **Subject Areas:** ESL
- **Class Sizes:** 60 to 80 students
- **Student Levels:** Intermediate

TEACHER RESPONSES (in the first week)

Aggregated Teacher Data (15 Teachers)

Practice Area	Mean Score
Planning Speaking Activities	3.2/5
Peer Interaction Usage	2.8/5
Technology Integration	2.4/5
Scaffolding Provision	3.1/5
Regular Assessment	2.6/5
Specific Feedback	2.9/5
Student Confidence (perceived)	2.7/5
Adequate Training	2.5/5

TEACHER RESPONSES (in the last week)

Aggregated Teacher Data (15 Teachers)

Implementation Ease	Mean Score
Structured Peer Interactions	4.2/5
Scaffolded Speaking Tasks	4.1/5
Assessment Strategies	3.9/5
Technology Integration	3.3/5

Strategy Effectiveness	Mean Score
Structured Peer Discussions	4.7/5
Progressive Scaffolded Tasks	4.5/5
Role-Playing Activities	4.4/5
Formative Assessment	4.3/5
Student Self-Assessment	4.1/5
Technology-Enhanced Practice	3.6/5

Observed Student Changes	Mean Score
Student Participation	4.4/5
Student Confidence	4.2/5
Communication Quality	4.1/5
Motivation to Improve	4.0/5
Voluntary Participation	3.9/5

5.2 Qualitative Findings

Qualitative analysis of data revealed several key insights: Students exhibited **higher levels of motivation** when speaking activities connected to their interests and real-world contexts. Practical tasks that had clear purposes beyond assessment generated more active participation.

Supportive classroom communities impacted students' willingness to take speaking risks. Classrooms with positive response to mistakes, respectful listening and constructive feedback showed greater improvement rates.

Educators' effective speaking behaviors encouraged the students, and their sharing of communication challenges they themselves faced, created more supportive learning environments.

Strategies corresponding with students' cultural norms proved most effective for diverse learners.

5.3 Strategy Effectiveness Analysis

Analysis of different pedagogical approaches exhibited varying levels of effectiveness:

Strategies- Most Effective:

1. Structured peer interactions alongwith with teacher facilitation.
2. Framed speaking activities with systematic progression.
3. Practical, purpose-driven communication tasks
4. Regular positive assessment with immediate feedback

Strategies- Moderately Effective

1. Technology-dependent practice without human interaction
2. Formal presentation style instruction
3. Grammar-focused speaking drills.

Strategies -Least Effective:

1. Unstructured speaking activities without clear objectives
2. Assessments of performance without preparation
3. Teacher-centered activities with minimal student interaction.

6. Discussion and Implications

The research findings emphasise the importance of systematic, structured approaches and effective strategies to developing students' speech competence . Supportive learning environments, appropriate challenges, and regular feedback mechanisms improves the students' confidence. When students feel safe to take risks, and do not fear to make mistakes, they engage wholeheartedly in the learning environment and demonstrate greater expertise to communicate.

The findings also highlight the importance of teacher preparation, training and professional development. Educators who comprehend the complexity of oral communication development and employ evidence-based strategies in their classrooms, create highly effective learning environments for the students.

6.1 Practical Implications for Educators

Based on the research findings, educators should consider implementing the following practices:

Set Learning Objectives: Students need to understand how their progress will be measured. Clear and explicit instruction about speaking skills clarify the learning process.

Provide Low-Risk Practice

Opportunities: Informal, casual, and occasional speaking activities help students develop fluency and confidence, and prepare them for higher-stakes communication tasks.

Give Positive Feedback: Feedback should be specific, prompt, targeting both strengths and areas for improvement. Balancing corrective feedback with encouragement motivates the students.

Nurture Inclusive Environments: Giving value to diverse communication styles while working toward common academic goals promotes a supportive learning environment.

6.2 Institutional Considerations

Educational institutions should adopt such a policy that supports effective oral communication instruction:

Teachers should be given training to adopt effective pedagogy, assessment techniques, and technology integration.

Speaking skills development should be integrated across subjects rather than confined only to language classrooms.

Institutional assessment policies should include oral communication competence alongside written communication skills.

Institutions need adequate resources for technological and professional development to support effective speaking instruction.

7. Future Research Directions

This study suggests certain directions for future research:

Observing students' performance over time can show whether improvements in speaking skills last and how these relate to other language skills, listening, reading, and writing.

Comparing students with different cognitive levels and from different social backgrounds can help find teaching methods that work everywhere in all settings. With modern digital technology, studies should explore how it can help improve students' speaking skills.

Research is required to explore the best methods, and professional development programs to train teachers effectively to teach speaking skills.

Conclusion

Improving students' speaking skills is a key goal in language pedagogy. This study explores

how planned, research-based methods boost speaking, confidence, and learning. Speech competence needs more than speaking opportunity—it requires support, structure, and assessment. Strong speaking skills also build critical thinking abilities. Institutions and teachers must focus on this area to prepare students for future success. Ongoing research and training are essential to reach this goal.

Acknowledgment

The authors and journal gratefully acknowledge the supervision and valuable guidance of Mr. Waqar Mahmood Khan, Lecturer in English at University of Okara, Pakistan.

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